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Research Article

AN EVALUATION TO ENROLL THE INDICATORS OF THE POSTOPERATIVE BLEAKNESS IN CAREFULLY TREATED PATIENTS OF PUNCTURED PEPTIC ULCER

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Abstract:

Background: Aperture of peptic ulcer is a perilous crisis and related with checked post careful dismalness

Objective: To enroll the indicators of the postoperative bleakness in carefully treated patients of punctured peptic ulcer.

Methods: A cross sectional examination was led at Surgical Departments of Allied and DHQ Hospital Faisalabad. Clinically and radiologically suggestive yet carefully demonstrated, 60 instances of the punctured peptic ulcer were incorporated into the investigation. Conceivable indicators were recorded on affirmation just as amid medical procedure. Postoperatively, patients were dealt with and followed up for the advancement of difficulty till the season of release. Contingent on the nearness/nonattendance of the post usable intricacies, patients were isolated into two gatherings. Information was entered and broke down by utilizing SPSS rendition 11.

Results: In our examination, age extended from 24-80 years. 26.7 percent of the cases had clinical highlights of stun at introduction. Smoking was noted in 47 percent of the cases. In 97% of the cases, the span of puncturing was under 1 cm while the greater part of the cases had measure of peritoneal spillage more than 1 Liter. The most widely recognized entanglement was wound disease. The vast majority of the patients were released home between the seventh and tenth postoperative days. Age more than 40 and male sex (p -esteem < 0.147) was not observed to be related with expanded danger of advancement of the post usable complexity. Confusion rate was observed to be very high for the patients showing following 72 hours of the improvement of the torment ($p=0.006$, OR=9.3). Different elements which demonstrated noteworthy distinction between the two gatherings for the advancement of confusion included stun at introduction (p -value= 0.032), history of smoking (p -value= 0.002) and the nearness of related medicinal disease (p -value= 0.01).

Conclusions: History of smoking, late presentation, presence of the associated medical illness and presence of shock at the time of presentation significantly influences the rate of development of post operative complications.

Key words: predictors, perforation peptic ulcer, complications.

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INTRODUCTION:

Puncturing of peptic ulcer is a perilous circumstance and an incessant reason for crisis admissions.[1,2] When this crisis is managed precisely, it is related with huge mortality and morbidity.[3] Currently utilized hazard stratification procedures are preferable indicators of mortality over morbidity.[4-5] The death rate has diminished surprisingly by the utilization of H-2 blockers yet the grimness is as yet the equivalent, might be a result of the reason that we are as yet not secure with the dreariness determinants.[5,6] It is a typical perception that postoperative dismalness related with punctured peptic ulcer prompts longer medical clinic remain and increasingly visit emergency clinic visits and confirmations influencing patient's general wellbeing and medical clinic costs. Therefore, it is very suitable to perceive the determinants of the postoperative bleakness with the goal that the specialists may well foresee the postoperative difficulties, and plan a superior administration heretofore. Present examination was led to enroll the indicators of imminent dreariness in carefully treated patients of punctured peptic ulcer.

MATERIAL & METHOD:

This investigation was directed at Surgical Departments of Allied and DHQ Hospitals Faisalabad. Study was begun on first June 2008 and was finished over a time of a half year. 60 patients of punctured peptic ulcer who experienced careful treatment were enlisted for concentrate by purposive inspecting. Subjects who had other gut pathologies like intestinal tuberculosis or typhoid aperture were rejected from the investigation. The factors estimated on affirmation included age, sex, length of agony, history suggestive of stun, history of smoking and nearness of related ailment/s like Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD), Hypertension (HTN), Diabetic Mellitus (DM) and Pulmonary Tuberculosis (TB). History suggestive of stun was characterized as expanded respiratory rate, cyanosis and adjusted condition of awareness notwithstanding a past filled with oliguria. Preoperatively, patients were revived with intravenous liquids; Ryle's cylinder desire and blood transfusion were done, where shown. They were begun on IV ceftriaxone and metronidazole. The analysis of aperture was made on clinical history, examination and nearness of gas under stomach on X-beam yet was affirmed just on investigation. The patients who experienced careful treatment, the stomach area were opened with a midline entry point. The peritoneal spillage if any was sucked out and estimated. The span of the aperture was noted. At that point the puncturing was shut by Graham's

omentopexy. In the wake of flooding with something like 3 liters of warm typical saline, the peritoneal depression was wiped altogether and mid-region was shut as it is done routinely in crisis. The choice to keep a channel depended on the level of peritoneal spillage, which was evaluated by estimating the measure of liquid in the suction bottle suctioned from opening the peritoneum till the phase of peritoneal lavage. The grimness determinants estimated amid activity were the measure of peritoneal spillage and the span of aperture. All patients postoperatively got intravenous liquids, triple routine anti-toxins and Ryle's cylinder yearning till the arrival of intestinal motility. Postoperative confusions were noted till the patient was observed fit enough to be released changing from 5 to 14 days. These included injury contamination, burst stomach area, hematemesis, enterocutaneous fistula and intraperitoneal ulcer. Proforma was utilized for the information gathering and SPSS adaptation 11 was utilized for information investigation. Elucidating insights were connected to decide the base age, greatest age and mean age. Frequencies were noted for age, sex, term since beginning of torment at introduction (<24 hours, 24-48 hours, > 48 hours), nearness or nonattendance of history of smoking, nearness or nonappearance of stun, nearness/nonappearance of related restorative ailment and sort of disease (DM, HTN, IHD, COPD), size of puncturing (<1 cm, >1cm), measure of peritoneal spillage (<1L, > 1L), kind of aperture (DU, pyloric, pre pyloric) sort of system (Graham's omentopexy, essential conclusion, pyloric rejection with gastro jejunostomy) number of inconvenience (None, one, two and three) and sort of complexity (wound contamination, burst guts, hematemesis, enterocutaneous fistulae, intraperitoneal abscesses). Emergency clinic stay was noted regarding least, most extreme and normal, in days. In the wake of taking note of the qualities of the investigation subjects and postoperative difficulties, subjects were isolated into gathering An and amass B relying on the nearness or nonappearance of postoperative entanglements. Frequencies of various determinants were noted in the two gatherings and chi-square test was connected to see the huge contrast (P-esteem <0.05) between the gathering An and aggregate B. Or on the other hand (Odd's Ratio) was determined to take note of the relationship of various determinants with danger of improvement of complexities.

RESULTS:

With respect to age of the examination subjects' base age was 24 years while most extreme age was 80 years. A large portion of the patients were more seasoned than 40 years old. Mean age was 46.08 years. Two pinnacles were watched, one at 45 years

old and the other at 60 years old.

80% of the patients were male. Lion's share of the cases exhibited inside 48 hours. Not many cases had length of agony >72 hours.

26.7 percent of the cases had clinical highlights of stun at introduction, though; smoking was noted in 47

percent of the cases. Concerning frequency of the related restorative sicknesses, greater part of the cases (43 cases) had no related medicinal ailment. COPD was noted in 8 patients. HTN was recorded in 4 while IHD and DM were available in 2 and 3 cases individually. (Figure I)

In practically 97% of the cases the extent of puncturing was under 1 cm. Just 2 cases had puncturing more than 1 cm. With respect to peritoneal spillage, the greater part of the cases had sum more than 1 Liter.

Sum more than 1 L was recorded in 34 cases. First piece of the duodenum was the most widely recognized site of puncturing, which was available in 52 cases. 5 cases had aperture in pyloric locale. Pre-pyloric puncturing was recorded in 3 cases. For the duodenol ulcer puncturing, Graham's omentopexy was done in 51 cases. 1 case with bigger aperture required pyloric prohibition with gastrojejunostomy. Instances

of pyloric and pre-pyloric puncturing experienced essential conclusion (9 cases).

Patients were followed up in the wards for the improvement of certain post usable intricacies. Lion's share of the patients, 36 cases (60%), grew none of the confusions. Fourteen cases created one confusion every, 8 cases created 2 difficulties each, while just 2 cases created 3 complexities each. The most normal entanglement was wound disease which created in 33 % of the cases. 10 cases created intraperitoneal abscesses, 5 created burst belly and one created enterocutaneous fistulae. None of the patients created haemetemesis. (Table II)

Table I: Complications

Wound infection	20(33.3%)
Intraperitoneal Abcesses	10(16.7%)
Burst Abdomen	5(8.3%)
Enterocutaneous Fistulae	1(1.7%)
Haemetemesis	0(0%)

The majority of the patients were released home between the seventh to tenth postoperative days. Normal emergency clinic stay was 8.75 days. Least medical clinic stay was 5 days while greatest was 14 days. Factual examination was done to survey the impacts of various pre-employable and intra-usable indicators on the advancement of the postoperative complexities. (Table II)

No huge distinction (Chi-square = 1.25, p-value= 0.25, OR 1.9) was noted between the two gatherings (Age <40 versus age > 40) being developed of the post usable complexities. Thus, sex was not observed to be the factor causing factually huge distinction between the gathering A and B. (Chi-square = 2.100, p-value= 0.147, OR 0.391)

Table II: Statistical analysis of the predictors

variables		Group-A (complications)	Group-B (complications)	Total	Chi-Square value	P value	OR
Age	<40	18	22	40	1.25	0.25	1.9
	>40	6	14	20			
	Total	24	36	60			
Sex	M	17	31	48	2.10	0.147	0.391
	F	7	5	12			
	Total	24	36	60			
Duration of pain at presentation	>72H	6	2	08	7.60	0.006	9.3
	<48H	9	28	37			
	Total	15	30	45			
Shock	Present	10	06	26	4.60	0.032	3.57
	Absent	14	30	44			
	Total	24	36	60			
H/O Smoking	Present	17	11	28	9.38	.002	5.51
	Absent	7	25	32			
	Total	24	36	60			
Medical Illness	Present	11	6	17	6.03	0.01	4.23
	Absent	13	30	43			
	Total	24	36	60			
Size of perforation	>1cm	02	0	02	3.1	0.07	Infinite
	<1cm	22	36	58			
	Total	24	36	60			
Amount of peritoneal spillage	>1L	16	18	34	1.62	2.02	2
	<1L	8	18	26			
	Total	24	36	60			

At the point when broke down for the span of agony at introduction, there was an exceptionally critical contrast between the two gatherings (Chi-square=7.60, p=0.006). Entanglement rate was observed to be very higher for the patients displaying following 72 hours as opposed to inside 48 hours of the improvement of the torment (OR=9.3). Different variables which demonstrated noteworthy distinction between the two gatherings for the advancement of inconvenience included stun at introduction (Chi-

square = 4.60, p-value= 0.032, OR=3.57), history of smoking (Chi-square = 9.38, p-value= 0.002, OR=5.51) and the nearness of related medicinal disease (Chi-square= 6.03, p-value= 0.01, OR 4.23). As to hazard factors noted per-operatively like the extent of the puncturing (Chi-square =3.1, p= 0.07, OR= endless) and measure of peritoneal spillage (Chi-square= 1.628, p=0.202, OR= 2), no huge distinction was noted.

DISCUSSION:

As of late there is pattern of fix of the peptic ulcer puncturing by laparoscopic approach [3,7,8], anyway the subjects in our examination experienced open fix. In addition, the method done in the majority of the cases was Graham's omentopexy. Along these lines, these outcomes will for the most part be material to open fix with Graham's omentopexy.

Expanded age is typically viewed as related with expanded danger of improvement of the post employable complication.[9-13] But in our examination age more than 40 was not observed to be related with expanded danger of advancement of the post usable confusions. This has likewise been accounted for by Sharma SS et al. in an ongoing study.[4] Although, they referenced that the explanation behind the distinction conceivably had been the lesser number of patients more seasoned than 60. In our examination this may not be the reason as the quantity of the patients more seasoned than 60 was 16. In our examination, sex was not the determinant of the postoperative entanglements. This factor has not been concentrated by others for as a hazard factor. A neighborhood contemplate referenced that late introduction was not a poor indicator of the result as it had not been related with expanded danger of improvement of the entanglement yet our investigation demonstrated that patients exhibiting following 72 hours as opposed to

those showing inside 48 hours of the advancement of the agony, were at more serious danger of advancement of the postoperative complications.[14] Late introduction as a hazard factor has been accounted for in numerous studies.[15,16] Stun has been accounted for as indicator of poor out result [4,17] due to its relationship with expanded occurrence and danger of postoperative inconveniences. Our investigation demonstrated the comparable outcomes. Smoking not just fundamentally affected the rate of advancement of the intricacies yet it was likewise observed to be related with expanded danger of creating them. As announced by numerous examinations [4,18], related therapeutic ailment is a determinant of the poor result, our investigation additionally portrayed that related restorative sickness was related with expanded danger of advancement of complexities.

No huge contrast was noted between the two gatherings when broke down for the extent of the puncturing and measure of peritoneal spillage. Size of puncturing (>1cm) is of exceptional concern due to two reasons. Right off the bat, we had just two patients with size of puncturing (> 1 cm) and them two created complexities however as the quantity of the patients was excessively less, no measurably huge distinction was found. Besides, Odd's proportion was observed to be boundless on the grounds that there was no patient without entanglement having size

more prominent than 1cm. We feel that these outcomes need further assessment in a bigger report. Ongoing examinations likewise don't have accord on this issue.[4,19]

As Sharma Ss4 detailed that stomach distension demonstrates the measure of peritoneal spillage in instances of the peptic ulcer and that it is factually, naturally and clinically important indicator of the hazard and number of postoperative inconveniences, we assessed the measure of the peritoneal spillage as a hazard factor. In any case, in our investigation, measurable examination neglected to demonstrate any relationship between the spillage >1L and the post employable difficulties.

CONCLUSION:

Our investigation uncovered that late introduction, history of smoking, nearness of stun at the season of introduction and nearness of the related therapeutic disease fundamentally impact the rate of improvement of post usable complexities in patients worked for aperture peptic ulcer.

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